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Perception of Kalesa Owners Regarding the Welfare Status of Kalesa Horses (*Equus caballus*) in Iligan City, Philippines

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Abstract.

This study aimed to gather baseline data on *Kalesa* owners' perceptions of horse welfare in Barangay Tambacan, Iligan City, Philippines. Employing a descriptive-correlational design, thirty (30) *Kalesa* owners were interviewed using a self-assisted questionnaire to assess key welfare indicators such as body condition, injuries, behavioral stress, and management practices. Findings revealed that most horses exhibited moderate body condition, minor injuries, and mild stress levels, suggesting an acceptable yet suboptimal welfare status. Although owners demonstrated basic knowledge of horse care, deficiencies were evident in providing proper bedding, ensuring adequate hydration during work hours, and preferring traditional remedies over professional veterinary treatments. Statistical analysis indicated no significant association between socio-demographic profiles and welfare status or perception. However, longer working hours were significantly correlated with a higher incidence of injuries. The study concludes by emphasizing the need for educational outreach programs, improved veterinary access, and the establishment of evidence-based care guidelines to enhance the overall welfare of working horses in the community.

Keywords: *Kalesa* horse, Horse, Welfare, Management, Perception

1.0 Introduction

The rhythmic clip-clop of hooves echoes through the streets of Iligan City, a sound deeply connected to its history and culture. The *Kalesa*, also known as the *Tartanilla*, has long been an iconic symbol of the city. Long before the arrival of modern vehicles, the *Kalesa* was the primary mode of transportation in the Philippines (Tour2Iligan, 2024). It contributes to the local economy and cultural heritage. During the 18th century, under Spanish colonial rule, the *Kalesa* was introduced to the Philippines by the Spaniards and served various purposes, such as daily transportation, emergency services, and even as ambulances during wartime (Seseka, 2024). It is a carriage with two large wheels on each side and a roof that provides shelter from the sun. Pulled by a horse, it can accommodate up to four passengers (Robles *et al.*, 2021). The *Kalesa* remains an important part of the country's history and culture. However, behind its beauty lies a complex issue: the welfare of these working horses is often compromised.

According to the Philippine Animal Welfare Society (2016), *Kalesa* horses are often overloaded and overworked, forced to work in poor health conditions without access to an equine veterinarian. Many carry six to eight people, excluding the *cocheros*, despite the Department of Tourism (DOT) regulations stating that only two passengers should be accommodated. Furthermore, in some Philippine cities where the *Kalesa* remains a tourist attraction, several online reports document cases of overworked horses subjected to the harsh realities of urban life. Gabbas (2024) notes that some handlers react aggressively, repeatedly whipping the animals to force them to stand, causing distress in horses

already showing signs of exhaustion, such as panting and drooling. Moreover, there have been cases in which, due to high urban temperatures, *Kalesa* horses have collapsed from exhaustion and dehydration while carrying passengers (PETA Asia, 2019). These cases may occur because some *cocheros* do not fully understand how to care appropriately for their horses, believing that feeding and watering them are sufficient before urging them to trot around the city to earn income (Yong, 2018). However, understanding animal welfare goes beyond basic feeding and grooming. Proper nutrition forms the foundation of a horse's health and well-being. Inadequate nutrition, coupled with poor management practices, can compromise all bodily systems and lead to a decline in overall welfare (Noble, 2023). Aside from nutrition, understanding equine behavior is also essential. Wolframm *et al.* (2024) emphasized that understanding how horses communicate and behave is crucial to ensuring their well-being. Their study also highlighted the importance of treating animals with respect and acknowledging their capacity to feel and experience emotions. Therefore, the general objective of this study is to assess the welfare status and perceptions of *Kalesa* owners in Iligan City, Philippines.

2.0 Methodology

This section describes the research design, locale and setting, respondents, instruments, data-gathering procedures, fecal analysis, statistical tools, and the ethical considerations observed throughout the study.

2.1 Research Design

This study used a descriptive-correlational design to describe the socio-demographic profiles of *Kalesa* owners, their knowledge and awareness of horse welfare and management, and the welfare conditions of *Kalesa* horses. It also examined the relationships between owners' characteristics, their knowledge and perceptions, and the welfare conditions. Descriptive research provides a clear description without manipulation, while correlational research identifies relationships among variables without establishing cause-and-effect (SurveySparrow, 2023).

2.2 Research Locale and Setting

This study was conducted in Barangay Tambacan, Iligan City, Lanao del Norte (Figure 1), from March to May 2025, using a simple random sampling procedure. According to PhilAtlas (2025), Iligan City is a coastal, highly urbanized area located in Northern Mindanao, Philippines. Geographically, it lies at approximately 8°14' N latitude and 124°15' E longitude and covers an area of 813.37 square kilometers (314.04 square miles).

Figure 1. Map of Barangay Tambacan, Iligan City, Lanao Norte, Philippines
<https://www.google.com/maps>

As of the 2020 census, the city has a total population of 363,115 (Philippine Statistics Authority, 2021). Its elevation varies significantly due to its diverse terrain, with an average elevation of approximately 229 meters (751 feet) above sea level. The highest point reaches around 1,067 meters (3,501 feet), while the lowest point is at sea level (Topographic-Map.com, n.d.). Iligan City is bounded to the south by the municipalities of Baloi and Linamon in Lanao del Norte, to the north by Lugait in Misamis Oriental, to the east by the territories of Lanao del Sur and Bukidnon, and to the west by Iligan Bay.

2.3 Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were exclusively Kalesa owners or operators. The list of Kalesa owners or operators was obtained from the City Agriculture Office or the Barangay office. In the absence of such a list, respondents were selected using simple random sampling.

2.4 Research Instruments

A 4-point Likert-scale questionnaire was used in this study to measure knowledge, awareness, and perceptions regarding horse welfare and management practices. The typical 4-point Likert item format consists of 4 (strongly agree), 3 (agree), 2 (disagree), and 1 (strongly disagree) (Joshi *et al.*, 2015). This scale allowed respondents to indicate their level of agreement or disagreement with statements on animal care, workload, housing, feeding, and veterinary practices.

2.5 Data Gathering Procedure

The respondents were personally interviewed using either self-assisted or self-administered survey questionnaires translated into their local dialect. The data gathered included the socio-demographic profiles of the Kalesa owners (age, educational attainment, and socio-economic status), their knowledge and awareness of horse welfare and management, the welfare status of the Kalesa horses (including health condition, feeding management, housing, and workload), and the owners' perceptions regarding horse welfare. These data were also used to evaluate the relationships between the owners' characteristics, their knowledge and awareness, and both the welfare status of the horses and their perceptions of horse welfare. Respondents were briefed on the questionnaire's content before completing it. The data from the completed questionnaires were consolidated, tabulated, and classified according to the parameters to describe the general characteristics of the respondents.

Fecal samples were collected from all experimental animals in the research area and handled in accordance with the Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee (IACUC) requirements, ensuring that the animals did not experience any discomfort or stress. A small amount of freshly collected feces was placed on a microscope slide and mixed with a drop of distilled water. A glass coverslip was then placed over the mixture, and the slide was examined under a compound microscope. Helminths were identified using the chart provided by Veterian Key (2017) and tallied. Additionally, the fecal analysis included morphological assessment (normal vs. abnormal feces) and identification of helminths infesting "Tartanilla" horses.

2.6 Fecal Analysis

A fecal analysis was conducted in this study to detect helminths infesting Kalesa horses. The Direct Smear Method was used to detect these helminths through microscopic examination. This method is effective for initial screening and provides a qualitative assessment of parasite presence (Foreyt, 2001).

2.7 Data Analysis

This study used both descriptive and correlational statistics to analyze the collected data. Descriptive statistics, such as percentages, means, and standard deviations, were used to summarize the socio-demographic characteristics of Kalesa owners, their knowledge and awareness of horse welfare and management practices, the welfare status of Kalesa horses, and the owners' perceptions of horse welfare. These descriptive measures provided a clear overview and interpretation of the data's patterns and distributions (Gravetter & Wallnau, 2017). Additionally, the Pearson Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r) was used to examine relationships between variables and to assess linear associations between continuous variables without implying causality (Field, 2018). This statistical test was applied to determine the strength and direction of relationships between:

- Kalesa owners' characteristics and the welfare status of Kalesa horses
- Kalesa owners' characteristics and their perceptions of horse welfare
- Owners' knowledge and awareness, and the welfare status of the horses
- Owners' perceptions of horse welfare and their knowledge and awareness of horse welfare

2.8 Ethical Consideration

The study followed established academic ethical standards. Respondents were informed about the purpose of the research, assured of their right to withdraw at any time, and guaranteed the confidentiality of their responses. No identifying information was included in any reports or publications. The research procedures complied with the ethical guidelines of Mindanao State University – Main Campus and the provisions of the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (Republic Act No. 10173).

3.0 Results and Discussion

This section presents the analyzed data collected from the respondents, accompanied by statistical findings and supported by relevant literature.

3.1 Kalesa Owner's Characteristics

Table 1 shows the socio-demographic profile of the respondents, revealing several factors that may influence their management practices and perceptions of horse welfare. In terms of age, the respondents are mostly young to middle-aged adults, comprising 50% of the sample, suggesting that younger adults remain actively engaged in Kalesa operations. Given that younger people are typically more open to adopting new practices and technologies, this is a positive indicator for potential welfare improvements (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations [FAO], 2014). The largest age group is 25 to 34 years, making up 26.7% of the sample, followed closely by the 18 to 24 age group at 23.3%. However, the presence of older respondents, including those aged 55 to 64 (13.3%), highlights the importance of traditional knowledge and long-standing practices that may shape approaches to horse care.

Regarding educational attainment, the majority of respondents have low to moderate levels of formal education. Specifically, 43.3% have completed high school, while 30% have only completed elementary school. Limited education may hinder respondents' ability to comprehend technical information related to animal welfare, proper nutrition, or parasite control. This emphasizes the need for extension services to use simple, practical, and visual methods when communicating concepts related to horse welfare (World Bank, 2018).

Table 1. Demographic and Socioeconomic Characteristics of Kalesa Owners

Variables	Frequency n=30	Percentage
Age range (Years)		
18-24	7	23.30
25-34	8	26.70
35-44	5	16.70
44-54	6	20.00
55-64	4	13.30
Mean		38
Educational attainment		
Elementary level	9	30.00
Elementary graduate	3	10.00
High school level	13	43.30
High school graduate	1	3.30
College level	3	10.00
College graduate	1	3.30
Socio-economic status (Income per day), PhP		
300-500	11	36.70
500-1000	18	60.00
1000 above	1	3.30
Mean		633.33

Regarding socioeconomic status based on daily income, a significant proportion of respondents earn below the region's minimum wage. Specifically, 36.7% earn between ₱300 and ₱500 daily, while 60% earn between ₱500 and ₱1,000, according to Wage Order No. According to RX-23 of the Department of Labor and Employment, the daily minimum wage for non-agricultural workers in Iligan City (classified under Wage Category I) is set at ₱438 (Department of Labor and Employment [DOLE], 2024). This comparison indicates that many Kalesa owners earn at or below the minimum wage threshold, which may limit their ability to invest in essential aspects of horse welfare, including proper nutrition, veterinary care, and adequate shelter.

3.2 Kalesa Owner’s Knowledge and Awareness of Horse Welfare and Management

Table 2 shows that the majority of respondents (53.3%) worked half days, 6 days a week, while 46.7% worked half days, 7 days a week. The average daily work duration was 5 hours, with 83.3% working 4 to 8 hours and 16.6% working fewer than 4 hours. While these working hours may seem moderate, they still reflect consistent daily exposure to work-related demands. More importantly, 66.7% of Kalesa owners reported often operating under variable weather conditions, such as alternating sun and rain, while only 33.3% described their work environment as mostly sunny. These environmental conditions directly affect both the operator and the horse. Exposure of horses to fluctuating weather, especially without proper shelter or rest, can contribute to thermal stress and reduce their overall welfare. Horses working under the sun for long periods are prone to dehydration, heat exhaustion, and fatigue.

Table 2. Evaluation of Kalesa Owners’ Understanding and Awareness of Equine Welfare and Management Practices

Variables	Frequency n=30	Percentage
Frequency of works		
Half day, 7 days a week	14	46.70
Half day, 6 days a week	16	53.30

Table 2 (continued). Evaluation of Kalesa Owners' Understanding and Awareness of Equine Welfare and Management Practices

Variables	Frequency n=30	Percentage
Duration of work per day		
Less than 4 hrs.	5	16.60
4-8	25	83.30
Mean	5	
Number of passengers carried per trip		
3-4 passengers	18	60.00
5 passengers	12	40.00
Mean	4	
Environmental condition during horse work		
Mostly sunny	10	33.30
Variable weather (alternate)	20	66.70

According to the International Society for Equitation Science (ISES), environmental conditions such as heat, humidity, and inconsistent weather patterns are known to impact the welfare and performance of working equids, especially in tropical settings (Burn, Dennison, & Whay, 2010). Consequently, welfare improvement strategies in Iligan City should consider not only the duration of the workload but also environmental exposure. Simple interventions, such as shaded waiting areas and consistent access to clean water, can significantly improve working conditions for both horses and their owners.

3.3 Welfare Status of Kalesa Horse

Table 3 shows that the majority of Kalesa horses (53.3%) were assessed as having moderate body condition, indicating that they are neither underweight nor overweight. According to the American Association of Equine Practitioners (AAEP), moderate body condition is acceptable for working horses. However, consistent monitoring is important to prevent under-conditioning, which can lead to reduced stamina and long-term health problems (Henneke, Potter, Kreider, & Yeates, 1983). Furthermore, body condition scoring is an objective technique for evaluating subcutaneous fat in horses, providing valuable insights into their nutritional status and overall well-being (Wellard, 2021). While 36.7% of horses were moderately thin, this suggests that a significant number may not be receiving optimal nutrition or may be experiencing energy deficits due to workload or insufficient feeding practices. Horses with lower body condition are at higher risk of health issues, reduced performance, and decreased resistance to disease.

Table 3. Evaluation of the Welfare Conditions of Kalesa Horses

Variables	Frequency n=30	Percentage
Body condition score (BCS)		
Thin	2	6.70
Moderately thin	11	36.70
Moderate	16	53.30
Moderately fleshy	1	3.30
Incidence of injuries		
No visible injuries	11	36.70
Minor injuries	19	63.30
Behavior		
No sign of stress	17	56.70
Mild Stress	13	43.30

Regarding behavioral stress indicators, 56.7% of the horses showed no visible signs of stress, suggesting they are generally accustomed to their environment and workload. However, 43.3% exhibited mild stress. Behavioral signs of stress, even if mild, should not be overlooked, as they can escalate over time if the underlying causes, such as heat, overwork, or poor management, are not addressed. As emphasized by the World Organisation for Animal Health (OIE, 2016), behavioral indicators of stress are reliable markers of welfare status. They should be considered alongside physical assessments to ensure holistic animal care.

3.4 Management Practices

Table 4 presents Kalesa owners' perceptions of horse welfare, focusing on management practices essential to their horses' well-being. The majority of respondents strongly agreed that shelters and stables must be regularly cleaned ($M = 3.87$), grooming should be done regularly ($M = 3.80$), and overworking should be avoided ($M = 3.80$). They also strongly agreed that clean drinking water must always be available ($M = 3.40$) and that management practices should be adjusted based on the horse's health and behavior ($M = 3.37$). Furthermore, respondents agreed with several other practices, including the need to provide a balanced diet ($M = 3.13$), allocate sufficient rest between work shifts ($M = 3.17$), monitor weight and body condition ($M = 2.93$), and follow a deworming schedule ($M = 3.03$).

However, respondents disagreed with the need to provide proper bedding ($M = 1.83$), indicating that most do not commonly use bedding materials such as straw. According to Cochran (2023) and Wilson (n.d.), proper bedding is essential for a horse's health, comfort, and overall welfare. It helps prevent joint and pressure injuries and supports good sleep quality. Bedding also absorbs moisture and waste, reducing the risk of hoof problems such as thrush, and helps control ammonia levels that can harm respiratory health. Clean, dry bedding reduces bacterial and mold growth, creating a safer, more hygienic environment for horses, particularly those kept in stalls.

Overall, the weighted mean score across all practices was 3.23, placing it in the "agree" category. This indicates a generally positive attitude toward implementing appropriate management practices.

3.5 Health Practices

Table 5 presents the respondents' level of agreement on various practices considered essential for maintaining the good health of horses. The overall weighted mean of 3.59 suggests strong agreement among Kalesa owners regarding the importance of proper health management for their horses. Based on the results, the highest agreement was on regularly checking the horse's overall health, providing veterinary care, recognizing early signs of illness or injury, and taking immediate action when needed. This indicates that most respondents are aware of the value of preventive health care in extending their horses' working capacity and overall health. Other practices, such as hoof maintenance and monitoring feeding behavior, were also strongly supported, showing that respondents recognize the importance of daily management routines in preventing health issues. Meanwhile, vaccination, environmental cleanliness, and supplement provision were rated slightly lower but still received agreement.

According to the American Veterinary Medical Association (n.d.) and Bukowski and Aiello (2024), preventive care and early treatment are critical for maintaining equine health. These authors emphasize that vaccines, maintaining a clean environment, and administering supplements are all essential components of good horse care. The results of this study align with commonly accepted guidelines for horse care, as the majority of respondents strongly agreed that regular veterinary check-ups, early diagnosis of disease or injury, immediate treatment, foot care, and monitoring of eating behavior are essential.

Table 4. Perceptions of Kalesa Horse Owners on Management Practices

Variables	Frequency				Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
	4	3	2	1		
1. Horses Must Have Access To Clean Drinking Water At All Times.	12	18	0	0	3.40	Strongly Agree
2. A Balanced Diet Appropriate For The Horse Must Be Provided.	4	26	0	0	3.13	Agree
3. Shelters/ Stables Must Be Regularly Cleaned And Maintained Regularly.	26	4	0	0	3.87	Strongly Agree
4. Sufficient Rest Periods Mut Be Allocated Between Work Shifts.	5	25	0	0	3.17	Agree
5. Grooming Must Be Done Regularly.	24	6	0	0	3.80	Strongly Agree
6. Weight And Body Condition Must Be Monitored Regularly.	1	26	3	0	2.93	Agree
7. A Schedule For Deworming And Parasite Control Must Be Followed.	2	27	1	0	3.03	Agree
8. Proper Bedding Must Be Provided.	1	0	22	7	1.83	Disagree
9. Overworking Beyond Capacity Must Be Avoided.	24	6	0	0	3.80	Strongly Agree
10. Management Practices Must Be Adjusted Based On Health Condition And Behavior Of The Horse.	12	17	1	0	3.37	Strongly Agree
Overall					3.23	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.74 -Strongly Agree; 1.75-2.49 -Disagree; 2.50-3.24 -Agree; 3.25-4.00 -Strongly Agree

Table 5. Perceptions of Kalesa Horse Owners on Health Practices

Variables	Frequency				Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
	4	3	2	1		
1. Horses should receive regular veterinary check-ups.	27	3	0	0	3.90	Strongly Agree

Table 5 (continued). Perceptions of Kalesa Horse Owners on Health Practices

Variables	Frequency				Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
	4	3	2	1		
2. Early signs of illness or injury must be identified.	26	4	0	0	3.87	Strongly Agree
3. Immediate care must be provided for illness or discomfort.	25	5	0	0	3.83	Strongly Agree
4. Proper vaccinations must be administered.	2	28	0	0	3.07	Agree
5. Hoof trimming and maintenance must be done regularly.	18	11	1	0	3.57	Strongly Agree
6. The environment must be kept clean and well maintained.	2	28	0	0	3.07	Agree
7. Supplements must be provided.	0	28	2	0	2.93	Agree
8. Feeding behavior must be monitored.	25	5	0	0	3.83	Strongly Agree
9. Immediate and appropriate action must be taken when signs of fatigue or injury appear.	27	2	1	0	3.87	Strongly Agree
10. In general, overall health and physical condition of the horse must be carefully considered.	29	1	0	0	3.97	Strongly Agree
Overall					3.59	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.74 -Strongly Agree; 1.75-2.49 -Disagree; 2.50-3.24 -Agree; 3.25-4.00 -Strongly Agree

3.6 Care and Treatment Practices

Table 6 presents the respondents' level of agreement on practices essential for the care and treatment of horses. The overall weighted mean was 3.23, indicating that respondents generally "agreed" with the importance of proper treatment and handling of horses, especially during times of injury or illness. Among the items, "Immediate treatment must be provided for injuries" received the highest rating, indicating unanimous strong agreement among all respondents. This reflects a high level of awareness of the urgency of promptly treating injuries to avoid complications and support a quicker recovery.

Other practices, such as "Humane restraint must be applied during treatment" (WM = 3.87, SD = 0.346) and "Traditional remedies can be applied alongside veterinary treatment" (WM = 3.53, SD = 0.507), were also interpreted as strongly agreed. This indicates that respondents value humane handling and view traditional remedies as complementary to modern veterinary care rather than as a replacement. Practices such as checking horse tack and harnesses for comfort, taking preventive measures against common injuries, implementing infection control, and allowing time for recovery were also widely accepted, aligning with good welfare practices for working equids.

However, the lowest-rated item, "Medications must be prescribed by a veterinarian" (WM = 2.43), was interpreted as disagree, revealing a significant gap in compliance with veterinary protocols.

This suggests that some respondents may not consistently consult veterinarians when administering medications. Instead, they rely more on traditional knowledge or believe that traditional remedies are sufficient for treating common ailments. However, the reliance on traditional remedies, while culturally embedded and sometimes beneficial, poses potential risks. A licensed veterinarian should always prescribe medications to ensure appropriate treatment and dosage. According to the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA, 2022), prescription animal drugs can only be dispensed by or on the lawful written order of a licensed veterinarian, and such medications must carry a cautionary label to ensure their proper and safe use. This requirement ensures that treatments are appropriate for the animal’s specific health needs and are administered safely.

Moreover, traditional or natural remedies used to support a horse’s health, such as herbal supplements, can offer benefits like aiding digestion or reducing inflammation. However, it is important to use this approach with caution. As Michael (2024) points out, “natural” does not always mean safe, and some herbs can interact negatively with prescribed medications or may not be suitable for specific health conditions. Misuse or overuse can lead to adverse effects rather than therapeutic outcomes.

Table 6. Perceptions of Kalesa Horse Owners on Care and Treatment Practices

Variables	Frequency				Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
	4	3	2	1		
1. Immediate treatment must be provided for injuries.	30	0	0	0	4.00	Strongly Agree
2. Medications must be prescribed by a veterinarian.	1	12	16	1	2.43	Disagree
3. Preventive measures must be taken to avoid common injuries.	5	24	1	0	3.13	Agree
4. Traditional remedies can be applied alongside veterinary treatment.	16	24	0	0	3.53	Strongly Agree
5. Adequate recovery time must be given after illness or injury.	2	28	0	0	3.07	Agree
6. Infection control measures must be applied to wounds.	3	27	0	0	3.10	Agree
7. Tack and harness must be checked for comfort.	4	26	0	0	3.13	Agree
8. Advice from experienced caretakers and vets must be considered.	2	28	0	0	3.07	Agree
9. Humane restraint must be applied during treatment.	26	4	0	0	3.87	Strongly Agree
10. Medical records of the horse must be maintained and updated regularly.	2	25	2	1	2.93	Agree
Overall					3.23	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.74 -Strongly Agree; 1.75-2.49 -Disagree; 2.50-3.24 -Agree; 3.25-4.00 -Strongly Agree

3.7 Workloads and Working Conditions

Table 7 presents the respondents’ level of agreement on practices essential to maintaining good working conditions for horses. The overall weighted mean was 3.12, which falls under the interpretation of “Agree,” indicating that most respondents recognize the importance of these practices in ensuring humane and safe working conditions for their horses. The highest-rated practice was “Horse welfare must be prioritized over work output,” which received a perfect score of 4.00, showing that all respondents strongly agreed.

Table 7. Perceptions of Kalesa Horse Owners on Workloads and Working Conditions

Variables	Frequency				Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
	4	3	2	1		
1. Workload must be within the horse’s physical limits.	16	13	0	1	3.47	Strongly Agree
2. Appropriate pulls weight must be applied.	4	24	2	0	3.07	Agree
3. Water must be provided regularly throughout the day.	0	0	14	16	1.47	Strongly Disagree
4. Work must be limited during extreme weather conditions.	7	22	0	1	3.17	Agree
5. Proper fitting harness and equipment must be carefully considered.	3	27	0	0	3.10	Agree
6. Proper hoof care must be regularly administered.	11	19	0	0	3.37	Strongly Agree
7. Energy levels must be closely monitored to determine work breaks.	5	25	0	0	3.20	Agree
8. Sufficient breaks during work hours must be provided.	2	12	16	0	2.53	Agree
9. Horses should have access to a suitable shelter when not working.	25	5	0	0	3.83	Strongly Agree
10. Horse welfare must be prioritized over work output.	30	0	0	0	4.00	Strongly Agree
Overall					3.12	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.74 -Strongly Agree; 1.75-2.49 -Disagree; 2.50-3.24 -Agree; 3.25-4.00 -Strongly Agree

This was followed by “Horses should have access to a suitable shelter when not working” (WM = 3.83) and “Workload must be within the horse’s physical limits” (WM = 3.47), which also received strong agreement. However, the practice “Water must be provided regularly throughout the day” received the lowest score (WM = 1.47), which was interpreted as strongly disagree. This suggests that many Kalesa owners do not follow routine hydration practices during work hours. This is a concern, as water is one of the most important nutrients that horses need and plays a critical role in digestion, thermoregulation, and overall performance. Proper hydration is essential for their health and efficiency. According to Shafiya (2024), it is important to provide water to a horse after exercising or during travel to replace lost fluids, but it should be given in moderation, as providing too much water too quickly or too cold can sometimes cause problems. Some respondents noted that giving water during working hours can lead to health issues; therefore, they prefer providing water after work, following a 15–20 minute rest period. While this practice may stem from traditional knowledge, withholding water for long durations, especially in hot or humid climates, increases the risk of dehydration, which can compromise performance and recovery, particularly in working equids (Burn, Dennison, & Whay, 2010).

Additionally, the statement “Sufficient breaks during work hours must be provided” received a weighted mean of 2.53, suggesting that rest periods may not be consistently observed. Providing adequate rest during working hours is essential for maintaining the health and welfare of working horses. Eurogroup for Animals (2019) and European Commission (2022) emphasized that working equids, such as those used in tourism, require sufficient breaks to prevent exhaustion and other health issues. Insufficient rest can lead to lameness, dehydration, and behavioral problems. In this study, Kalesa horses only work for an average of 5 hours per day, with a minimum interval of 5 minutes per

trip, allowing horses to rest during these breaks. These short breaks may help reduce fatigue, though they may not fully substitute for longer, structured rest periods needed to prevent stress, especially under variable environmental conditions.

3.8 Relationship Between Kalesa Owners’ Characteristics and the Welfare Status of Their Horses

Table 8 shows the statistical relationship between selected Kalesa owners’ characteristics, such as age, educational attainment, and socio-economic status, and three welfare indicators of Kalesa horses: body condition score, incidence of injuries, and behavioral stress. All p-values were greater than 0.05, indicating that none of the variables tested showed a statistically significant relationship. This suggests that owner age, level of education, and income do not significantly influence the physical or behavioral welfare status of Kalesa horses in this study. These results imply that other factors beyond the socio-demographic profile of the respondents, such as management practices, environmental conditions, and access to veterinary services, may play a more crucial role in influencing horse welfare.

This finding aligns with studies emphasizing that management practices, handler experience, and environmental factors are more reliable indicators of horse health and well-being than demographic characteristics alone (Burn, Dennison, & Whay, 2010; Pritchard, Lindberg, Main, & Whay, 2005). Additionally, the lack of significant correlation might reflect a common cultural understanding or shared practices among owners, regardless of age or educational attainment, especially in a traditional livelihood like Kalesa operation. These results underscore the need for welfare-focused education and training programs that target all Kalesa owners uniformly, regardless of socio-demographic differences.

Table 8. Relationship Between Kalesa Owners’ Profiles and the Welfare of Their Horses

Variables	p-value	Interpretation
Age		
1. Age of the Kalesa owners and the Body condition score of the Kalesa horses.	0.093	Not significant
2. Age of the Kalesa owners and the incidence of injuries of Kalesa horses.	0.672	Not significant
3. Age of the Kalesa owners and the behavior of Kalesa horses.	0.742	Not significant
Educational Attainment		
1. Educational attainment of Kalesa owners and the body condition score of the Kalesa horses.	0.474	Not significant
2. Educational attainment of Kalesa owners and the incidence of injuries of Kalesa horses.	0.436	Not significant
3. Educational attainment of Kalesa owners and the behavior of Kalesa horses.	0.132	Not significant
Socio-economic Status		
1. Socio-economic status of Kalesa owners and the body condition score of the Kalesa horses.	0.115	Not significant
2. Socio-economic status of Kalesa owners and the incidence of injuries of Kalesa horses.	0.875	Not significant
3. Socio-economic status of Kalesa owners and the behavior of Kalesa horses.	0.725	Not significant

3.9 Relationship Between Kalesa Owners’ Characteristics and Their Perception of Horse Welfare

Table 9 shows the relationship between Kalesa owners’ characteristics and their perception of horse welfare. The results indicate that there is no significant relationship between age, educational attainment, or socio-economic status of Kalesa owners and their perception of horse welfare. This suggests that the socio-demographic characteristics of Kalesa owners do not significantly influence how they perceive the welfare of their horses. Instead, perceptions regarding horse welfare may be shaped more by shared experiences, cultural practices, or community norms than by individual characteristics such as age, educational attainment, or income.

These findings are consistent with previous studies indicating that attitudes toward animal care are often influenced by firsthand experience rather than formal education. According to Hemsworth, Jongman, and Coleman (2021), knowledge and practical experience, rather than demographic characteristics, are closely associated with horse owners’ attitudes toward care and management. Similarly, Te Velde, Aarts, and Van Woerkum (2002) highlight that perceptions of animal welfare are often informed by cultural and social norms, especially in communities where animal use is part of traditional livelihoods. Based on the results of this study, Kalesa owners appear to have very similar opinions regarding the significance of horse welfare, despite differences in age, education, or income.

Table 9. Relationship Between Kalesa Owners’ Profiles and Their Views on Horse Welfare

Variables	p-value	Interpretation
1. Age of the Kalesa owners and their perception of horse welfare.	0.478	Not significant
2. Highest educational attainment of Kalesa owners and their perception of horse welfare.	0.327	Not significant
3. Socio-economic status of Kalesa owners and their perception of horse welfare.	0.265	Not significant

3.10 Relationship Between Kalesa Owners’ Knowledge and Awareness of Horse Welfare and Management and the Welfare Status of Kalesa Horses

Table 10 shows the relationship between Kalesa owners’ knowledge and awareness of horse welfare and management and the welfare status of Kalesa horses. Among the indicators assessed, only the duration of work per day was found to have a significant relationship with the incidence of injuries ($p = 0.048$), indicating that longer working hours may contribute to a greater risk of injuries. This implies that overworking horses without adequate rest may compromise their safety and health. Other indicators had p-values greater than 0.05, suggesting no significant relationship between these variables.

The implication of this finding is that working hours must be managed carefully, as continuous daily work without sufficient rest increases the risk of physical strain and exhaustion, which can result in injury. Therefore, regulating working hours and ensuring adequate rest are essential aspects of good horse management, particularly for working equids such as Kalesa horses. These findings are supported by Pritchard, Lindberg, Main, and Whay (2005), who highlight that poor management practices, including long working hours and insufficient rest, are associated with increased injury and lameness in working horses. In addition, Burn, Dennison, and Whay (2010) emphasize that proper work-rest cycles and workload management are critical for the welfare of working horses in urban settings. Regular monitoring and adjustment of work schedules can thus help minimize injuries and improve welfare outcomes.

Table 10. Relationship Between Kalesa Owners’ Knowledge and Awareness of Horse Welfare and the Horses’ Welfare Status

Details	Variables	p-value	Interpretation
1. Frequency of works	Body condition score	0.115	Not significant
	Incidence of injuries	0.509	Not significant
	Behavior	0.425	Not significant
2. Duration of work/day	Body condition score	0.066	Not significant
	Incidence of injuries	0.048	Significant
	Behavior	0.421	Not significant
3. Number passengers carried/day	Body condition score	0.923	Not significant
	Incidence of injuries	0.258	Not significant
	Behavior	0.356	Not significant
4. Environmental condition during horse works	Body condition score	0.085	Not significant
	Incidence of injuries	0.063	Not significant
	Behavior	0.279	Not significant

3.11 Relationship Between Kalesa Owners’ Perception of Horse Welfare and Their Knowledge and Awareness of Horse Welfare and Management

Table 11 shows the relationship between Kalesa owners’ perception of horse welfare and their knowledge and awareness of horse welfare and management. The results indicate that there is no significant relationship between the variables. All p-values were greater than 0.05, suggesting a lack of statistical significance. This demonstrates that even though Kalesa owners may hold certain beliefs or perceptions about horse welfare, it does not necessarily mean they consistently follow good care practices. The discrepancy between what they believe and what they actually do emphasizes the necessity of training programs that teach proper and practical horse care techniques in addition to raising awareness.

In support of this, Luna et al. (2023) found that higher levels of empathy and accurate pain perception in horse owners were correlated with better welfare conditions in working horses. This implies that enhancing owners' emotional understanding and recognition of equine needs can lead to improved welfare outcomes. In addition, Golding et al. (2023) found that horse owners' knowledge and perceptions of common clinical conditions significantly impact their management decisions, further emphasizing the importance of comprehensive education in equine care.

3.12 Stool Assessment

Healthy horse manure typically consists of well-formed, moist fecal balls that are easily breakable, with a mild earthy smell and brown color (Figure 2). A slightly greenish tint from fresh grass is considered normal. On the other hand, watery consistency, unusual colors, foul odor, or undigested feed can indicate potential health issues (Bazay, 2024; FeedXL Equine Nutrition Team, 2020). In the present study, the majority of the fecal samples collected exhibited characteristics of healthy manure, such as proper consistency, color, and odor, indicating that most of the horses were in good health.

Table 11. Relationship Between Kalesa Owners’ Perception and Knowledge of Horse Welfare and Management

Variables	p-value	Interpretation
1. Owner’s perception of horse welfare and the horse frequency of work	0.855	Not significant
2. Owner’s perception of horse welfare and the horse duration of work per day	0.325	Not significant
3. Owner’s perception of horse welfare and the horse number of passengers carried per trip	0.586	Not significant
4. Owner’s perception of horse welfare and the environmental conditions during horse work.	1.000	Not significant

Figure 2. Horse Specimen Stool

Table 12 shows the common parasites found in this study, including *Strongyle*, *Parascaris equorum*, and *Trichostrongylus axei*, which are similarly identified as common gastrointestinal parasites in horses (Nielsen, 2019). Strongyles are considered the most prevalent internal parasites affecting horses, with an estimated global prevalence of 80–99% among equids (McNeill, 2023). Horses acquire these parasites by ingesting contaminated pasture, hay, or grains. Moreover, *P. equorum*, also known as ascarids, is one of the most common parasites infecting horses and can negatively affect their health, performance, and productivity (Zelpina et al., 2022). The most frequently identified internal parasite in

this study was *Cyathostoma* spp., also known as small strongyles, accounting for 21.05% of cases. Small strongyles, or cyathostomins, are among the most widespread parasites affecting horses, thriving across diverse climates and management systems, including tropical, temperate, and cold environments (Husted *et al.*, 2009).

Other suspected internal parasites included *Parascaris equorum* (15.79%) and *Trichostrongylus axei* (15.79%), both of which primarily affect horses with higher incidence in younger animals (less than one year old) and older horses (Figure 3). While some infected horses may not exhibit clinical signs, heavy infestations can lead to weight loss, reduced energy, and gastrointestinal disturbances, as noted by the Western College of Veterinary Medicine (2021). Horses with compromised immune systems, particularly those kept in poor living conditions, are more vulnerable to severe infections.

Table 12. Parasites Identified in Horses

Parasites	Frequency n=38	Percentage
<i>Cyathostoma</i> spp	8	21.05
<i>Parascaris equorum</i>	6	15.79
<i>Trichostrongylus axei</i>	6	15.79
<i>Strongylus</i> spp.	2	5.26
<i>Oxyuris equi</i>	4	10.53
<i>Fasciola hepatica</i>	1	2.63
<i>Dicrocoellum dendriticum</i>	1	2.63
<i>Strongyloides westeri</i>	2	5.26
<i>Habronema</i> spp	4	10.53
<i>Anoplocephelia</i> spp	2	5.26
<i>Dictyocaulus amfieldi</i>	2	5.26

Figure 3. Type of Parasite

4.0 Conclusion

In conclusion, the study underscores the importance of educational programs that target Kalesa owners, focusing on best practices for horse care, including proper feeding, hydration, rest, and preventive health measures. Enhancing access to veterinary services is crucial to ensure timely diagnosis, treatment, and vaccination, which can reduce the incidence of injuries and diseases among working horses. Additionally, providing practical, easy-to-follow care guidelines can bridge the gap between owners' perceptions and actual management practices, ultimately promoting the overall health, welfare, and productivity of these animals.

5.0 Contribution of the Authors

Jeanny G. Guliman: The author conducted data collection, analyzed the findings, and wrote the entire manuscript.

Jesse Jay O. Villanueva: The author conceptualized the study, developed the research instrument, and supervised the validation process with subject-matter experts.

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7.0 Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest concerning the publication of this study.

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